

THE IMPACT OF Financial INCLUSION on GENDER, POVERTY And Employment Creation

A Case study of Financial Institutions in the Sudan

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to investigate and analyze poverty problem. During the last decade unsustainable external debt compelled most of these countries to enter into a painful adjustment process in the late 1980. The economic reforms demanded by this process soon created important distribution effects. At the local level many people lost their jobs and became poor and excluded as a result of measures taken to downsize public administrations and privatize public enterprises. The opening of borders and the subsequent inflows of goods and services caused local industries that were not competitive to close down and lay-off workers. In the long-run, the economic growth achieved through these transformations is expected to create enough new job opportunities to compensate for the present loss in wealth and stability. In the short term, however growth has not been steep enough to absorb those who were laid off. It also could not provide enough resources to enable those who were unable to extricate themselves from poverty to survive. Poverty and exclusion as a consequence, quickly spread out and became more than the moral concern they had been for centuries. They became in fact the most pressing political, economic and social issues that governments needed to address.

The main aims of this study is: 1. To examine existing measures to help the poor in their entrepreneurial activities. 2. To highlight the necessity of the extension of financial inclusion. 3-highlighting the importance of the social protection nets.4. To identify areas where there is no policy at all, and to examine the absence of relevant on the promotion of small enterprises. 4. To identify policies, measures and priority actions

to accelerate the process of enhancing women's entrepreneurs participation in the economy.

The study is based on the following hypotheses: During the 1990, the provision of financial services dealing with small deposits and loans microfinance-and particularly micro credit has been increasingly acclaimed as effective means of poverty reduction.

Economic inequality between and within household is likely to be associated with concentrations of political and social power.

1. The research achieved the following results:

- 1) In the Sudan access to credit allows poor people to take the advantage of economic opportunities. While increased earnings are by no means automatic, clients have overwhelmingly demonstrated that reliable sources of credit provide a fundamental basis for planning and expanding business activities. It is evident that clients who join and obtain micro credits have better economic conditions and have also shown that over a long period of time many clients do actually come out of poverty.
- 2) By reducing vulnerability and increasing earnings and savings, financial services allow poor households to make the transformation from "every-day survival" to "planning for the future". Households are able to send more children to school for longer periods and to make greater investments in their children's education. This fact is ascertain by the result of the questionnaire conducted for the purpose of this study and 84% of the families interviewed has children in school, 13% their children not admitted to school and 3% of them left school.
- 3) Increased earnings from financial services lead to better nutrition and better living conditions, which translates into a lower incidence of illness. Increased earnings also mean that clients may seek out and pay for health care services when needed, rather than go without or wait until their health seriously deteriorates. This point is ascertained by the fact that poor people are vulnerable and uncovered by health insurance schemes. It is worth mentioning here that

universal coverage is crucial for the poor. So the extensions of micro health insurance facilitate the sustainability of their work.

2. Recommendations

Relying on the above the following recommendations could be suggested:

2.1. In the area of poverty reduction

- 1) An urgent need to conduct the poverty map for the Sudan.
- 2) Recognizing the importance of labor as an asset of the poor, a labor intensive development intervention should be adopted.
- 3) Promoting self-employment as a poverty alleviation intervention.
- 4) At the macro-level the identification of the socio-economic policies and pro-poor strategies is essential as an anti-poverty strategy. A national poverty alleviation strategy is a must.
- 5) At the micro-level a poverty alleviation plan of action is a must.
- 6) Drawing attention to the importance of education and equity of opportunities and choice.
- 7) Combating unemployment in its different types and among different segment in the society.
- 8) Identification of the term poverty there is no concrete definition of poverty in Sudan yet. The Ministry of Welfare adopted the definition of had alkifaya and had alkfaf as the poverty definition.
- 9) The necessity of the identification of the poverty line in Sudan as the Academician adopted the global definition (less than one dollar a day) poverty line, so there is important need to define both poverty and those suffering from it.
- 10) Facilitating access to microfinance as a poverty alleviation intervention

3. Recommendations in The Area of Gender

The central recommendations in the area of gender are as follows:

- 1) Ensure women and men equal access to resources, education, labor, land, capital and technology.
- 2) Promoting women access to micro- finance, credit and enterprise development.
- 3) Avoiding the stereotypic views which perpetuating gender-based sectoral and occupational segregation.
- 4) Regulating women work in the informal sector where women represents the bulk of the disadvantaged labor force.
- 5) Promote women ability in decision making and their organization in women unions, and community based organizations.
- 6) Removing legislation barriers which perpetuate women subordination and gender gaps in income/capability poverty.
- 7) Enhancing gender capabilities literacy, formal education, market-elevant skill training particularly vocational training.
- 8) Advocating at the micro level for a conducive environment and to a better understanding of poverty gender specific aspects.
- 9) Advocating for the design of programs addressing socio-economic equity in the community, translated into development intervention at the community in a sustainable micro project.

3.1. Recommendations in the Area of Micro-finance

1. Government efforts in the Sudan should focus to increase the provision of formal financial services to poor people with special concentration on the rural areas.
2. Make available effective access of the poor and make the financial system respond to the demand for microfinance.
3. At the micro level the development of an effective competent financial institutions is essential.

4. At the macro level the development of policies and creation of enabling environment that protects and supports the development of the financial inclusion for the poor are essential.
5. At the local level the development of the required institutional capacity building in terms of human capital and financial infrastructure.

The opportunities for microfinance in the Sudan is very large due to the potential demand, both in North and Southern parts of the country Commercial banks are interested and competent, as it appeared from the results of the questionnaire conducted for the purpose of this study. Bank of Sudan is ready to exercise leadership, as it appeared from its initiative in a workshop conducted in (28 February 2006) to come out of a new vision for the development of the microfinance industry in the Sudan.

مستخلص الدراسة

الهدف من هذه الدراسة هو تقصي وتحليل مشكلة الفقر. أثناء العقد الأخير في نهاية الثمانينات من القرن الماضي أجبرت الديون الخارجية غير المستدامة غالبية الدول النامية للدخول في عملية التكيف المؤلمة. الإصلاحات الاقتصادية التي تتطلبها هذه العمليات عجلت بخلق آثار هامة تتعلق بعدم المساواة في توزيع الثروة. على المستوى المحلي تم إخضاع الهيئات والمؤسسات العامة للخصخصة كنتيجة لتنفيذ سياسات التحرير الاقتصادي فقد معظم الناس وظائفهم وأصبحوا فقراء.

فتح الحدود وانسياب المنتجات والخدمات أدى إلى توقف الصناعات المحلية التي لا تملك القدرة التنافسية وإلى تسريح العاملين فيها. على المدى الطويل يتوقع أن تؤدي هذه الإصلاحات إلى النمو في الاقتصاد وخلق وظائف جديدة تعمل على تعويض الفاقد في الثروة والاستقرار. على المدى القصير فالنمو الاقتصادي لا يسرع بالقدر الذي يمكنه من امتصاص فائض العمالة، كما أنه لا يمكن أن يوفر موارد كافية يمكن أن تقي هؤلاء من الفقر وتمكنهم من البقاء كنتيجة حتمية فقد انتشر الفقر والاستبعاد بسرعة وأصبح من أكثر الالتزامات الأخلاقية ومن الموضوعات الاجتماعية والسياسية والاقتصادية التي يتحتم على الحكومات مواجهتها.

تلخصت الأهداف الأساسية لهذه الدراسة في الآتي:

1. مراجعة المقاييس الحالية لمساعدة الفقراء في أنشطتهم الريادية.

2. تقييم أثر التمويلات الصغيرة التي تقدمها المنظمات الحكومية والمنظمات الطوعية لتخفيف الفقر بالتركيز على أهمية توفير شبكة الحماية الاجتماعية.
3. تحديد الفجوة في السياسات الداعمة للأعمال الصغيرة.
4. تحديد السياسات والمقاييس وأولويات العمل لتنفيذ والإسراع بتحقيق مشاركة المرأة الريادية في الاقتصاد.

استندت الدراسة على الفرضيات التالية:

- أثناء عقد التسعينات من القرن الماضي أضحى توفير الخدمات المالية التي تشمل على الإيداع والقروض الصغيرة وبالتحديد التمويلات الصغيرة أداة فاعلة لتخفيف حدة الفقر.
- عدم المساواة الاقتصادية في المنزل غالباً ما تكون مرتبطة بتركيز القوى الاجتماعية والسياسية.

1/ توصلت الدراسة إلى النتائج الآتية:

1. الوصول إلى التمويل يمكن الفقراء من استغلال إيجابيات الفرص الاقتصادية. بينما تعتبر زيادة الدخل تلقائية، إلا أنها تخول للمستفيدين مرتكزاً أساسياً للتخطيط والتوسع في الأنشطة الاقتصادية. الشاهد أن الذين انضموا أو حصلوا على قروض صغيرة نجد أوضاعهم الاقتصادية قد تحسنت كما أنهم وفي مدة قصيرة يمكنهم تجاوز مشكلة الفقر.
2. بتقليل الانكشاف وزيادة الدخل والإدخار، تمكن الخدمات المالية الفقراء من التحول الحقيقي من البقاء على الدخل اليومي إلى التخطيط للمستقبل. كما يمكنهم من إبقاء أطفالهم بالمدرسة لمدة أطول و الاستثمار الأكبر بتعليم أبنائهم. هذه الحقيقة أكدت نتائج الدراسة حيث وضح أن 84% من الأسر التي تمت مقابلتها لديهم أطفال بالمدارس، 13% لم يتم قبول أطفالهم بالمدرسة، 3% ترك أطفالها الدراسة.
3. زيادة الدخل من توفر الخدمات المالية تؤدي إلى التغذية الجيدة وإلى تحسين الأوضاع المعيشية، والتي تنعكس في تقليل الأمراض. زيادة الدخل تعني أيضاً أن المستفيدين يمكنهم من مقابلة تكلفة العلاج عند الحاجة، بدلاً من الانتظار حتى تتدهور حالتهم. هذه النقطة أكدت حقيقة أن الفقراء أكثر عرضه وأكثر انكشافاً وغير محميين بالتأمين الصحي. الجدير بالذكر أن الحماية الصحية أمر هام للفقراء. عليه فان مد نطاق التأمين الصحي الصغير (الميكرو) يعمل على استدامة العمل.

2/ استناداً على النتائج اعلاه يمكن اقتراح التوصيات التالية:

1-2- توصيات في مجال تخفيف الفقر:

1. هنالك ضرورة ملحة لعمل خارطة للفقر في السودان و تبني استراتيجيه العمالة الكثيفة لتوسيع فرص عمل للفقراء.
2. ضرورة تبني الاستخدام الذاتي كمدخله لمكافحة الفقر, ووضع تعريف معين للفقر, تحديد خط الفقر الملائم للسودان.
3. على المستوى الكلى ضرورة تحديد السياسات الاقتصادية والاجتماعية والاستراتيجيات المناصرة للفقراء كإستراتيجيه حتميه لمكافحة الفقر. ووضع خطة عمل لمكافحة الفقر على المستوى المحلى.
4. مكافحة البطالة بمختلف اشكالها وسط الشرائح المختلفة في المجتمع. العدالة في توزيع الفرص.
5. تفعيل وصول الفقراء الى التمويل الاصغر كمدخله لتخفيف الفقر و تفعيل الشمول المالي.

2-2 التوصيات فى مجال النوع:

- 1.التأكيد على الوصول المتساوي للمرأة و الرجل للموارد (الارض - راس المال – العمل - التكنولوجيا).
- 2.التأكيد على وصول النساء للتمويل الاصغر, القروض و تنمية المشروعات الصغيرة.
- 3.الابتعاد عن الآراء النمطية التي تعمل على تأطير التفرقة الهيكلية و القطاعية الخاصة بالنوع.
- 4.تنظيم عمل المرأة في القطاع غير المنظم حيث تمثل المرأة فيه ثقل قوة العمل البائسة.
- 5.تعزيز قدرات النساء في مجال صناعة القرار و التنظيمات النسوية القاعدية.
- 6.ازالة التشريعات التي تعمل على استدامة خضوع المرأة و فجوة الدخل، و فقر القدرات.
- 7.تعزيز قدرات النساء في مجال التعليم و التعليم النظامي و التدريب.
- 8.الترويج لإيجاد بيئة ملائمه للفهم الصحيح للفقر و النوع.
- 9.الترويج لتصميم برامج لتحقيق العدالة الاجتماعية والاقتصادية في المجتمع و ترجمتها لبرامج اجتماعيه مستدامه.

3-2 توصيات فى مجال التمويل الأصغر و الشمول المالي:

1. ضرورة تركيز الجهود الحكومية لزيادة الخدمات المالية للفقراء بتركيز خاص على المناطق الريفية.
2. تحقيق فعالية وصول الفقراء للتمويل و جعل الخدمات المالية تستجيب للطلب على التمويل الاصغر.
3. ضرورة تطوير مؤسسات ماليه فعاله على المستوى القطاعي.
4. ضرورة تطوير السياسات و البيئة الصديقة لحماية و دعم و تطوير القطاع المالي للفقراء.

CHAPTER ONE

Introduction

1.1. Introduction: -

Background:

The spread of poverty phenomenon has thus come to affect the households in the developing countries of which Sudan is no exemption. However, the subordination and marginalization of the poor is not only economically based, but it has also been enhanced by various socio-economic and political factors resulting in the reproduction of the system as a whole. Views, that are expressed to provide a framework for this paper, were considered within the context of the politico-socio-economic development of the Sudan.

It is becoming more and more evident to the world that there is a close linkage between women and development. Women being the second half of the society must have affect and being affected by the general situation of development in the country. Therefore, they should be seen as central components in formulating and implementing policies and programs aimed at accelerating socio-economic development. (Boserb,1978).

Microfinance has been recognized by donors and development agencies as an effective tool for poverty reduction and employment creation, Microfinance has developed largely in reaction to the failure of policies of the kind intended to reach significant numbers of poor people, and the exclusion of women from access to financial services, as well as setting requirements which excluded poor people, mainstream development oriented credit was subsidized and therefore seen as unsustainable. Two of the innovations of microfinance have been used to eliminate the need for collateral and to develop ways in which financial services targeted the poor can be self- financing and thus not dependent on external subsidy.

According to the state of Microcredit Summit Campaign Report 2011, 14.2 million of the world poorest women now have access to financial services through specialized Microfinance Institutions MFIs, Banks, NGOs, and other non Banking

financial institutions. These women account for nearly 19.3 million of the world poorest people now being served by Microfinance Institutions most of these women have access to credit to invest in business that they own and operate themselves. The vast majority of them have excellent repayment records in spite of the daily hardship they face. Contrary to the conventional wisdom, they have shown that it is a very good idea to lend to the poor and to women.(Global Microcredit Summit Report2011)

While women access to financial services has increased through out the world but still it is not to the extent which help them to invest and help themselves to escape poverty trap or unemployment. It is limited by the disadvantages they experience because of their gender.

The concept of Gender and Development:

Development affects women and men differently. The after effect of colonialism and the peripheral position of Third World countries in the world economy exacerbate the effect of sexual discrimination on women. The penetration of capitalism leading to modernization and restructuring of the traditional economies, and the new faith in the market epitomized by the economic structural adjustment programs (SAPS) had significant implications for poverty incidence and strategies to combat it often increased the disadvantages suffered by women.

Women in developing countries carry a double burden of work as they cope of housework, rearing and caring of children and food production. (Boserb 1997).

The status of women is relatively low compared to that of men counterparts. This has been deeply rooted in culture, religion, and socio-political background. Apart from this, the socio-economic development is curtailed without the full participation of women all fields, and ways to integrate women in the socio-economic process remain to be real indicators of human justice and equality.

The approach to development of women that is concerned centrally with the position of women and their strategic interest is the “empowerment approach”

If women are to attain justice in society, the structures of subordination should be transformed into changes in law (civil codes, property rights, labor codes, social and legal institutions).

“Engendering” the discourse on poverty has crucial implication for translating aspects of capability poverty into effective action, specifically in terms of skill training and the link with productive employment and underpinned by the recognition that labor markets are gender institutions.(Kamla Baisn,2000).

Recognizing the importance of labor as an asset of the poor which requires support to attain its full potential we have to focus on promoting labor-intensive development intervention including the capacity of the poor to engage in self-employment through a multi-services approach which involves the provision of arrangement of entrepreneurship development, technical and financial services, and the strengthening of self-organization and negotiating capacity of the poor, for poor women in particular, this implies advocating for their representation in policy dialogues at all levels. And supporting “Safety nets that address poor women’s employment and income-generation activities, not only their social welfare needs.

In terms of promoting self-employment as a poverty alleviation intervention specifically income generation projects for women, lessons learnt in various development contexts reflect that women usually lack access to micro-credit or related income-generation facilities, which in turn confined them to the traditional source of credits or finance, which make their work insecure, being stuck in labour-intensive employment characterized by poor working condition and long hours lack of skill upgrading and promotion, and economic insecurity.

So evidence indicates that “gender” based right differentials characterize labor markets in every country thus reveal that discriminatory policies of the state plays an important role in viewing women as full partners in development. In other words more serious attention needs to be accorded to the crucial question. Whether or not (trade relation) outcomes and policies contribute to more egalitarian gender relations in terms which are less prejudicial to women’s income earning capacity or well-being. (Ann Oakly 1955).

What is Financial Inclusion: -

Financial inclusion means that all people and businesses have access to and are empowered to use affordable, responsible financial services that meet their needs. **These** services include payments, savings credits, and insurance.

Young women face many gender-based barriers as they navigate major life transitions, with life-long effects. A new CGAP Working Paper finds that in addition to improving financial skills and savings levels, financial inclusion initiatives may also improve health and livelihood outcomes when combined with other interventions.

Financial inclusion can be transformative for people and businesses historically, people with low incomes, women, and other socioeconomically marginalized groups have been underserved by financial institutions. Without access to formal services and the freedom and skills to use them, they have often relied on informal unregulated financial tools.

The concept of financial inclusion grew out of the micro credit movement of the 1970s. Today, it is an important part of the global development agenda.

Significant progress has been made over the years toward universal financial inclusion. However, 1.4 billion adults are still unable to participate in the formal financial sector, and women remain less likely to have accounts than men.

Women's income poverty will tend to be further exacerbated by gender specific legal constraints with implication for perpetuating female socio-economic exclusion. Specifically because of traditional perception of male gender roles, and where legislation in this respect is either weak or absent, women generally do not have direct access to social benefits (health insurance, pensions schemes, housing, credit). Evidence suggests some links between women's income poverty and the vulnerability to balancing the responsibilities of their reproductive roles with the demands of their economic activities.

Therefore, gender specific constraints impede female access to productive resources and exacerbate their vulnerability to poverty.

Micro-finance, which implies small scale credit and savings services for poor people, is increasingly seen as a key tool to reduce poverty and promote economic and social development. The last few years have seen the creation of the Consultative Group to Assist the Poor (CGAP) a World Bank initiative to promote microfinance. The Micro-credit Summit Campaign, which calls for the development of sufficient micro-financial services to reach a 100 million of the world's poorest families by the year 2005, as well as numerous other initiatives. These initiatives are intended to contribute to the scaling up of existing microfinance institutions (MFI) and the creation of new ones.

Worldwide, there is a trend to provide micro-financial services, primarily to women. It is widely believed that increasing women's control of cash can contribute to their empowerment. Furthermore women's greater access to cash and their increased autonomy in its use is often believed to enhance their control of their own household resources, thus leading to an increased spending on children's welfare.

Initiated Subsidized Credit Programmes which aimed to assist small farmers to increase their productivity and incomes, and reduce their dependence on money lenders, similar models were pursued by post independence government, in South Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa (Adam and Von Pischke, 1992) and are in many countries still common today. However and despite good intentions, the impact of those policies has been rather limited, largely because they are based on misconceptions about the nature of poverty.

Firstly, they often assume that the poor are small farmers, ignoring the diversity of poverty. This has meant that landless laborer's and the urban poor have often been ineligible for credit secondly; the focus on small farmers has led a requirement of land as collateral. This has served to exclude sharecroppers, people in regions with communal land tenure systems, as in much of Africa, as well as landless rural people or the urban poor. The focus on small farmers has also excluded women in parts of the world where they do not (or are believed not to) farm, as have requirements for land as collateral since women rarely hold formal title to land.

Women's access to credit is generally lower than men's in most societies, due to institutionalized discrimination against them.

Informal credit markets-where rich individuals will lend to others at high rates but without collateral are similarly widespread. In many places these are the only financial services available to poor or marginalized people; in others they co-exist with microfinance programmes. Where their use strengthens social ties that can be called upon in the futures, they may be preferred to microfinance programmes, especially those which set extensively on onerous conditions for participants. However, systems of this kind are largely invisible to policy makers, and their benefits, as well as their limitation largely ignored.

Governments efforts to increase the provision of microfinance or formal financial services to poor people go back at last to the nineteenth century. In South Asia Colonial administrations identified money lenders as key perpetuations of exploitation and poverty in rural areas (Mc Groger, 1994, Rutherford, 1995) therefore, for these reasons even Poverty Oriented Financial Services Programmes (POFSPs) have often been captured by better-off people.

1.2. Statement of the Research Problem

Poverty has become the primary concern of developing countries. During the last decade unsustainable external debt compelled most of these countries to enter into a painful adjustment process in the late 1980. The economic reforms demanded by this process soon created important distribution effects. At the local level many people lost their jobs and became poor and excluded as a result of measures taken to downsize public administrations and privatize public enterprises. In the long-run, the economic growth achieved through these transformations is expected to create enough new job opportunities to compensate for the present loss in wealth and stability. In the short term, however growth has not been steep enough to absorb those who were laid off. It also could not provide enough resources to enable those who were unable to extricate themselves from poverty to survive. Poverty and exclusion as a consequence, quickly spread out and became more than the moral concern they had been for centuries.

The new bottom-up approach broadened the scope of anti-poverty policies and gave a special role to credit in the overall poverty eradication process.

Among the first most publicized examples of bottom-up efforts to fight poverty the Grameen Bank in Bangladesh went as far as to call credit “a right of the poor” other experiments stressing the importance of the informal sector as a source of employment and income for the poor were also developed in Africa and Latin America.

1.3. Research Significance

Microfinance has developed largely in reaction to the failure of policies of the kind intended to reach significant numbers of poor people, and the exclusion of women from access to financial services, as well as setting requirements which excluded poor people, mainstream development oriented credit was subsidized and therefore seen as unsustainable. Two of the innovations of microfinance have been used to eliminate the need for collateral and to develop ways in which financial services targeted the poor can be self-financing and thus not dependent on external subsidy.

1.4. Objectives of the Study

1. To examine existing measures to help the poor in their entrepreneurial activities.
2. To assess the impact of microfinance carried by Governmental Organizations (GO's) and None-governmental organizations
3. To highlighting the necessity of the extension of financial inclusion and importance of the social protection nets.
4. To identify areas where there is no policy at all, and to examine the absence of relevant policies on the promotion of small enterprises.
- 5-Support services, and promote the participation of the commercial Banks.

1.5. Research Hypotheses

During the 1990, the provision of financial services dealing with small deposits and loans-microfinance-and particularly micro credit has been increasingly acclaimed as effective means of poverty reduction.

Economic inequality between and within household is likely to be associated with concentrations of political and social power.

A full understanding of poverty must take into consideration that inequalities do accelerate poverty. This means recognizing economic inequalities and other inequalities including those of gender have reciprocal impacts. Gender inequalities, for example are not only damaging to the interests of women but also damaging to people's livelihood strategies as a whole. Analysis of poverty situation has referred to "feminization of poverty".

2.5 Scope of the research:

Cooper and Schindler (2008) view the scope as the breadth and depth of a topic's coverage (by time frame, geography, criteria for inclusion etc). In the proposed study, the scope is reviewed in terms of the subject, area and time. In terms of subject, it is limited to the discipline of socio-economic development, (microfinance as a tool for poverty reduction.) With respect to geographical (area) scope, the proposed study was conducted in the Republic of Sudan when the country witnessed the growing of massive poverty is widespread and perceive in urban and rural area due to the relatively low incomes, inequality in income distribution.

1.6. Methods of data collection

Social scientists use three main methods for collecting data: These are: (1) observation, (2) The use of existing data, and (3) asking questions. Relying on this the researcher decided that the three techniques are going to be used for the following reasons:

- (1) Observation is superior to other methods of data collection as it describes the certain features of past situations the use of observation allows the researcher to describe what actually happens in reality.
- (2) Use of existing secondary source material.
- (3) The interview as it used in most developing countries is a prominent technique in collecting data.
- (4) PESTEL analysis, used as an analytical tool which considers external factors and helps the planners and policy makers, to think about their impacts.

2-6. Difficulties and constraints: - The major constraints was the reluctance of the officials to give information and respond to the questionnaire. Inadequate of official information regarding the percentage of poverty, poverty line identification and the number of the poor households.

2.6.2- Conventional Banks are avoid targeting the poor as the poor lacked Banks collateral.

CHAPTER TWO

Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

2.1. Introduction: -

The aim of this chapter is to review some of the basic conceptual theoretical framework, views and approaches about poverty, gender, and micro-finance to reflect the extent of financial inclusion.

Views, that are expressed to provide a framework for this study, were considered within the context of the politico-socio-economic development of the Sudan. Bearing in mind the incorporation of capitalist relations in the social formation of the world economy, the penetration of the capitalist relations in the social formation of the Sudanese society, has affected both women and men. The spread of poverty phenomenon has thus come to affect the households in the developing countries of which Sudan is no exemption. However, the subordination and marginalization of the poor is not only economically based, it has been enhanced by various socio-economic and political factors resulting in the reproduction of the system as a whole.

This chapter is composed of three sections, section (1) aimed to review some of the relevant literature on poverty, its definitions, concepts, measures and dimensions. Section (2) aimed to review the available literature about gender concepts, definitions dimensions, and roles implications. Section (3) aimed to review the literature available in the field of microfinance, financial inclusion, definitions, concepts and its impact in poverty reduction.

Section one

2.1.1. Introduction: -

This section is set -out to review some of the basic conceptual frame work, views, and approaches about poverty such as poverty definitions, measures, trends in poverty over time its dimensions, understanding of poverty, poverty reduction strategies, poverty and development, social capital and the effects of poverty, safety nets, and social policy. As regard poverty within the development discourse in Africa, the 1950s and 1960 were dominated by the modernization paradigm which emphasized growth as defined in the rate of growth of gross national product. The model aimed to increase overall national economic growth through a policy of urban-based industrialisation. The economy was conceived as a reality of traditional and modern values. Which basically meant western capitalist values. The development path was considered as a shift from traditional society to modern industrial society, and within this continuum poverty was seen as the sub-culture which could be broken through modernization coming from foreign capital and industrialization.

By the 1970s and 1980s the limitations of the modernization model were clear and even where good growth rates had been achieved, there was limited income redistribution and the problems of poverty and unemployment were increasing. New paradigms were emerging in most capitalist economies: redistribution with growth became the new approach arguing for strategies to address basic needs (Chenery *et al* 1974).

By the late 1980s many African countries were experiencing economic crises of one form or another. The crises was the result of many factors, of which the primary one, was poor economic performance induced in part by the lack of structural transformation of the economy. Both the multilateral and bilateral donors were shifting back their faith to the market, as the neo-liberal paradigm once again gained the ascendancy and established its dominance. There was a political resurgence of the new right, which strongly argued for free market economics and a retreat of the state from the development scene. The global debt crises and the world recession strengthened this resurgence forcing most governments to comply with the neo-bilateral economic model. The new faith in the market epitomized by the economic structural adjustment programmes (SAPS) had significant implications for poverty incidence and strategies to combat it. In most cases SAPS meant that countries were compelled to devalue their

currencies scrap all quota restrictions on imports and slash tariffs to decrease their current account deficit, raise interest rates, tighten the money supply and purge the state from active participation in the economy, eliminate subsidies-sharing in education and health. This-on good and cost new laissez fairyism increased the burden of adjustment on the poor (Degefe 1994).

The reality of growing urban poverty has been compounded by the high rates of urban growth experienced in all the major centers of the developing world, coupled with the poor economic performance experienced by many countries. The 1990s, therefore, saw a growing urgency by the international community to address these growing crises. This has been revealed through the major international conferences held in 1990s.

The 1990 World Development Report highlighted the uneven spread of the burden of poverty with nearly 50% of the worlds poor living in South Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa. The latter region while accounting for a smaller proportion in absolute population terms, still has a disproportionate share globally given its population size.

Writing about poverty over the last decade, and the critical importance of poverty reduction in development have been increasingly recognized by governments and international organizations. This has gained further imeetis from the commitment of governments in Copenhagen Declaration of the Social Development (1993).

In a seminal essay on the interdisciplinary debate in the definition and measurement of poverty, Martin Greeley explores at least two major approach to thinking about and comparing poverty across different societies. One approach is the traditional use of absolute poverty lines to define and quantify the indigent. By this approach the poor are those whose income falls below particular point in the income distribution curve at which accounting for food and none food expenditures, it is impossible to buy a nutritionally adequate diet. This framework has been criticized for difficulty adequate diet and the challenges inherent to understanding such complex issues as the distribution of food within households, for which it cannot be disaggregated; it is generally regarded as a fairly standardized and objective approach to the measurement of poverty. Greeley argues that poverty lines allow for the consideration and comparison of basic human needs across varied societies, and thus serve as a critical instrument in the generation of international policy and data on the amelioration of human suffering.

One of the most influential of the broad-viewed formulation of welfare is Amartya Sin's rights based theory of distribution in which income serves only as an entitlement by which individuals purchase commodities that allow them to attain certain capabilities. For Sen., individual advantage ought to be assessed in terms of individuals freedom to achieve, rather than in terms of goods such as food alone. Sen believes that welfare models should consider human functioning such as the opportunity to escape avoidable mortality, to achieve self-respect, and to partake in community life. For Sen, expanding capability sets would in fact be the real measure of development, and by inference, poverty would represent a state of limited or obstructed capabilities. Sen's work has been critical to the formulation of human development measure (e.g. the human development index) employed by multilateral organizations and national governments.

No matter the approach espoused in the analysis and conceptualization of poverty, Greely argues that one common element is the "recognition of primacy of material need at low levels of well-being" Though the debate over what constitutes poverty is an important one.

According to the United Nation Report of the General Assembly (2000) there has been a marked increase in the level of poverty in all of the countries in the African region, although with varying degrees of severity. Overall, the poverty level in Eastern Europe and the countries of the common-wealth of Independent States increased from 4 percent of the population in 1988 to 32 percent in the mid nineties.

Although a recent report vividly demonstrates the importance of reducing poverty in the commonwealth and of action by commonwealth , as one third of the commonwealth two billion people live on less dollar a day and 64 % on less than two dollars a day.

In the absence of a sustainable economic turnaround in most other countries with economic in transition, poverty has continued to expand as a result of low average wages, growing long term unemployment, and the low level of social transfers. Combined with the higher cost of living and growing income differentiation.

The poverty line, a figure cutting the distribution of income of population into two unequal parts. those individuals showing a real household expenditure per capita lower than this figure are to be considered as poor while those a above it are not.

Women's income poverty will tend to be further exacerbated by gender specific legal constraints with implication for perpetuating female socio-economic exclusion. Specifically, because of traditional perception of male gender roles, and where legislation in this respect is either weak or absent, women generally do not have direct access to social benefits (health insurance, pensions schemes, housing, credit). Evidence suggests some links between women's income poverty and the vulnerability to balancing the responsibilities of their reproductive roles with the demands of their economic activities.

Therefore, gender specific constraints impede female access to productive resources and exacerbate their vulnerability to poverty.

Micro-finance, which implies small scale credit and savings services for poor people, is increasingly seen as a key tool to reduce poverty and promote economic and social development. The last few years have seen the creation of the Consultative Group to Assist the Poor (CGAP) a World Bank initiative to promote microfinance. The Micro-credit Summit Campaign, which calls for the development of sufficient micro-financial services to reach a 100 million of the world's poorest families by the year 2005, as well as numerous other initiatives. These initiatives are intended to contribute to the scaling up of existing microfinance institutions (MFI) and the creation of new ones.

Worldwide, there is a trend to provide micro-financial services, primarily to women. It is widely believed that increasing women's control of cash can contribute to their empowerment. Furthermore women's greater access to cash and their increased autonomy in its use is often believed to enhance their control of their own household resources, thus leading to an increased spending on children's welfare. Despite these facts still Women's access to credit is generally lower than men's in most societies, due to institutionalized discrimination against them.(Islah Elawad PhD2006) .

Microfinance is nothing new, communities worldwide have developed their own financial systems which enable people to manage shortfalls of cash, and provide lump sum amount for particular occasions and safe places to save. For example Rotational Savings and Credit Savings Associations (ROSCAs) where group members pay a certain sum into a common pot every week, and a different member takes the money each week are common throughout the world. Informal credit markets—where rich individuals will lend to others at high rates but without collateral—are similarly widespread. In many places these are the only financial services available to poor or marginalized people; in others they co-exist with microfinance programs. (Susan Johnson and Rogaly 1997, Elawad 2006).

Access for All is more than a slogan. For 10 years, the world's largest aid agencies have worked together under the banner of the Consultative Group to Assist the Poor (CGAP), committing people, money, and countless hours to building more inclusive financial systems—systems that work for the poor. (Global Microcredit Summit Report 2011)

The CGAP family has helped build near universal consensus around the fundamentals of an inclusive financial system: from regulation and supervision at the policy level, to financial reporting and disclosure at the institutional level, to fairly priced products at the client level.

The CGAP Key Principles of Microfinance—which call for, among other things, more enlightened policies from donor countries—have been endorsed and championed by the Group of Eight industrial nations as well as governments throughout the developing world. Queen Rania of Jordan has made them the foundation of her work as chairperson of CGAP's microfinance initiative for the Arab world. Worldwide, “best practice” microfinance is becoming standard practice. Almost 600 microfinance institutions now report to the Microfinance Information exchange (MIX), the CGAP-created portal that has become “the Bloomberg of microfinance” to give a no-nonsense picture of transparency, sustainability, and growth in the microfinance sector. Indeed, mainstream rating agencies themselves are now including microfinance institutions in their reviews.

The picture so far is breathtaking. Where small, heavily subsidized microcredit schemes used to be the norm, hundreds of profitable microfinance providers of all institutional shapes and forms are now offering a wide range of financial services—money transfers, deposit services, and insurance—to ever-larger numbers of poor people in their communities. In a sure sign that microfinance is going mainstream, domestic and international commercial banks are now entering the fray, motivated by the excellent performance of poor clients and the promise of new information and delivery technologies to reduce cost and risk.

Examples abound. In Kenya, Equity Bank is opening 18,000 accounts of poor people each month. K-Rep bank, which began as a small nongovernmental organization, is

today a fully converted commercial bank—among the fastest growing in the country. India's ICICI Bank, through partnerships with microfinance institutions and nongovernmental organizations, has added 1.2 million microfinance clients in the past three years. In Mexico, Compartamos has grown from a donor-supported institution to a licensed financial institution serving more than 400,000 clients and regularly tapping the local bond markets.

More than 3 billion poor people seek access to basic financial services essential to managing their precarious lives. At CGAP, work in developing countries to build financial systems that are inclusive, systems that serve the entire population and not just a tiny minority. Why? Because of the cascading power of microfinance. And because how access to loans and deposit services has empowered millions of people to work their way out of poverty. (Access for all Frankfurt School 2008)

As put by CGAP “For many of the world's poor, microfinance works. But to reach the billions more people who could benefit from financial services, we need to provide access on a much more ambitious scale. We need to convince commercial banks and other financial and nonfinancial institutions that poor and low-income clients represent a viable business proposition.”

These big-picture issues are indeed crucial for reducing poverty in the long term. But for the 3 billion people living on less than \$2 per day, access to even basic financial services can be a critical ingredient in alleviating poverty.

Most people in the developing world—that is, the majority of the world's population—do not have access to formal financial services. Very few benefit from a savings account, loan, or convenient way to transfer money. Those who do manage to, say, open a bank account, are often faced with sub-optimal services.

Why should we care? Because the lack of access to financial services prevents poor and low-income people from making everyday decisions that most people around those dinner tables take for granted. Financial services for the poor, often referred to as microfinance, cannot solve all the problems caused by poverty. But they can help put resources and power into the hands of poor and low-income people themselves, letting them make those everyday decisions and chart their own paths out of poverty. The potential is enormous, and so is the challenge. (Global Microcredit Summit Report 2011)

-Feminization of poverty

If female poverty, whether children, youth or adults, is mostly an income and/or educational poverty, for an Arab women it is more comprehensive than that, because cultural dimensions are added and are represented in the values and perceptions which are prejudiced against gender. These can be seen in the educational opportunities, types of work, and wages among males and females. Social dimensions are added to the above and are related to the paternalism dominant. And if there are possibilities and capabilities for numbers of males to come out poverty belts and pass its borders, those possibilities and capabilities are definitely smaller in the case of women as such and Arab women in particular in current social setting which is still depends on the gap between males and females. If we take into consideration the fact that poverty goes back deep into the past and is almost related to the beginnings of social division of labor between male and female, and the separation of production beyond the

household area, it is also obvious that although globalization raised ideas on human rights and the necessity of participation, the effects of that globalization have added to women much of justice and burdens the things that led to raising the concept of feminization of poverty, and also led some to go further and say that current poverty is almost having a female face. (Poverty Coping Strategies among women in Sudan, Islah Elawad 2000)

The extent of complication of women's poverty issue and its need for various knowledge and planning and exceptional efforts become clear to us. In the light of surveys, studies and research that dealt with the effects of poverty in the characteristics of Arab women and the chances of their empowerment, the following ideas can be extracted:

- Most of data and information indicate that the distribution of means of preparing and qualifying Arab women are endowed chances of impoverishment of women and her social and political marginalization in many circumstances and this is proved by the literacy among females in (1997) was less than 46.45% whereas it was higher one and a half times among males (70.6%) in the same year.
- Women opportunities for economic empowerment are shrinking, the matter that increases their impoverishment possibilities became the shrinking of chances of economic empowerment is related to the quantity and equality, and returns of labor.
- The percentage of the economic activity is considerably low among Arab women at the age of 15 and above, it does not exceed the fifth of their total number, the rate of 19.2 according to the 2000 year statistics.
- The working relationships where the Arab women are involved show that they are either working without getting wages like housework or working in the informal sector in the rural areas while in urban areas working in the public sector.
- Unemployment analysis in the Sudan between the years 1975-1995 assures the fact that unemployment among females has almost multiplied in the mentioned period and increased among the educated women.
- Women's status refers to their overall position in the society. It is often described in terms of the women ability to control important events in their life and the more that they have options as men in the same age group and social class. Thus it is a reflection of the level of justice in that society.

- The status of women is relatively low compared to that of male counterparts. This has been deeply rooted in culture, religion, and socio-economic and political background. Apart from this the socio-economic development is curtailed without the full participation of women in all fields, and ways to integrate women in the socio-economic development process remain to be real indicators of human justice and equality.
- Generally, the change in the position of women can be attributed to different processes and mechanisms that are accelerated by circumstances and historical events. These circumstances and historical incidences are universally interlinked with the economy and material well-being of the people, in terms of livelihoods and survival.
- Even Since 1975, a uniform conclusion of the international research on women is that with a few exceptions, relative access to economic resources, incomes, and employment have worsened, their burdens of work have increased and their relative absolute health, nutritional and educational status have declined. What is significant is that this decline in women's situation has occurred in spite of all the information, publicity and pressures surrounding women in the last two decades.
- Policy approaches that have been successively adopted in an attempt to change women's status have been described as welfare, equity, antipoverty, efficiency and employment.

The overall goal of awareness of gender issues is to achieve equity and efficiency, and productivity by involving women and men at all levels of the planning and management of the development process. Their joint and equal involvement leads to efficiency of planning and to cost reduction. Accommodating gender needs offers a chance to place investments more precisely and to avoid planning mistakes and imperfections especially with matters related to their life needs. Further, providing forums for gathering views and encouraging debates on incorporates gender interests into strategic planning and puts gender responsive measures into practice. For development to be engendered and not engendered, these steps of achieving efficiency, equity and productivity have to ensure. Equity in gender calls, means to increase participation of women and men, a balanced allocation, management and utilization of available resources by women and men. It is a process of reduction

where some gains and loses are made by both women and men depending on the circumstances of each gender.(Islah ElAwad PhD 2006).

Understanding gender concepts: -

Gender refers to the qualitative and interdependent character of-women's and men position in society. Gender relations are constituted in terms of the relations of power and dominance that structure the life chances of women and men. Thus, gender divisions are not fixed biology, but constitute an aspect of the wider social division of labor and this, in turn, is rooted in the conditions of production and reproduction and reinforced by the cultural, religious and ideological system prevailing in a society.

The relations between men and women are socially constituted and not derived from biology. Therefore the term "gender relations" should distinguish such social relations between men and women from those characteristics which can be derived from biological differences. In this connection "sex" is the province of biology, (i.e. fixed and unchangeable qualities) while "gender" is the province of social science, (i.e. qualities which are shaped through the history of social relations and interactions).

The word gender is now being used socially or as a conceptual category, and it has been given a very specific meaning. In its new incarnation gender refers to the socio-cultural definition of men and women, the way societies distinguish men and women and assign them social roles. It is used as an analytical tool to understand social realities with regard to women and men.

When we use the word gender we mean the socially constructed roles, status, expectations, and relationships of women and men. Similarly, when we use the terms "gender equity" and "gender equality" we are not suggesting an equality based on sameness but rather one based on difference. The process of achieving gender equality is a strife for justice through the transformation of constraining gender roles and ideologies that influence organizational structures, values, behavior, and outcomes.

Conceptual issues: from Sex to WAD, WID & GAD: -

The term women and development (WAD) and the term women in development (WID) were coined in the early 1970s by the Women's Committee of Washington, DC, chapter of the society for International Development, (a network of female development professionals who were influenced by the work in Third World development undertaken by Ester Boserup and others new anthropologists (Boserup1970, Tinker 1982, and Maguire 1984). The term was very rapidly adopted by the United States

Agency for International Development (USAID) in their so-called women in development (WID) approach, the underlying rationale of which was that women are an untapped resource who can provide economic contribution to development. (Women's Committee of Washington 1970s)

Gender mainstreaming is a key to ensuring efficient use of resources and sustainability. It ensures that gender is accommodated and there is gender sensitivity right from conceptualization to realization of final outcome of any activities and issues. (Understanding Gender p.4.)

Inequality means different things to different people whether inequality should encapsulate ethical concepts such as desirability of a particular system of rewards or simply means differences in income is the subject of much debate. Here we can conceptualize inequality as the dispersion of the distribution, whether that can be income, consumption or some other welfare indicator or attribute of a population. Obviously, poverty and equality are very closely linked-for a given mean income, the more unequal the income distribution, the larger the percentage of the population living in income poverty.

Section Two

Credit and Equity Support as Components of Self Employment

2.3. Credit and Equity support as Components of Self Employment

2.3.1. Introduction

This section deals with the exploration of the concepts and definitions of the term Micro-finance, as well as its implications in the development process. It deals also with the constraints and central challenges that have been and remain important for work in the field of enterprise development. And review problems facing women in this area.

From the 1950s, governments and international aid donors subsidized credit delivery to small farmers in rural areas of many developing countries. It was assumed that poor people found great difficulty in obtaining adequate volumes of credit and were charged high rates of interest by monopolistic money lenders. Development finance institutions, such as Agricultural Banks, were responsible for the delivery of cheap credit to poor farmers.

Since the 1980s development theories have increasingly argued for the provision of small loans to micro-entrepreneurs as an effective policy instrument in the fight against poverty.

During the 1990s, the provision of financial services dealing with very small deposits and loans “microfinance”, and particularly the provision of micro credit have been increasingly acclaimed as an effective means of poverty reduction. There is continuing and quite rapid improvement in understanding how financial services for the poor can best be provided.

Micro-credit is the latest development fashion, and it has even received the ultimate accolade of a world summit, it is not generally appreciated, however, that there is a wide variety of quite different approaches to the profitable delivery of financial services to the poor. Such services have for many years been provided by different types of institution, including traditional commercial banks, NGO's and the much publicized new generation institutions.

Micro-finance has been described as a new world, but if it can be genuinely profitable, why is it that this business opportunity has for so long gone unrecognized? In fact, of course, it is not a new world at all. The potential of savings, credit and other financial services to support the livelihoods of poor people is increasingly being recognized. Micro-finance interventions can raise incomes, contribute to individual and household security, and change social relations for better. But it cannot be assumed that

they will do so. It may often be more effective in terms of poverty reduction to support existing user-owned services or to link people up with established banks.

Many microfinance programs primarily or exclusively target women, for a variety of reasons. These reasons include redressing their exclusion from formal financial services and promoting their autonomy and empowerment through increasing their access to cash.

Three dimensions of women's empowerment could be credit such as access to and control of financial resources; influence within their households; and their position in the community. (USAID annual Micro enterprise Results Report for 2000). Several assumptions are frequently made about women's access to and control of financial resources. Firstly, it is assumed that women tend to retain control of any money that they can borrow or save. Secondly it is further assumed that they can build up independent resources, and finally this greater access to money strengthens women's position within the household.

Research has shown that women's incomes are more likely to go towards meeting their families' basic needs than men. Thus, enhancing the capacity of women from low income and asset-poor households to generate income at decent levels is an important element in any strategy to promote socio-economic development. In recent years, opportunities for wage employment have diminished, for women even more than for men.

According to USAID annual Micro enterprise Results Report for 2000, approximately 70% of USAID support MFIs clients were women.

However, this shows considerable variation among regions with percentage of women client ranging from 27% in the Near East to 87% in Asia.

Microfinance institutions around the world have been quite creative in developing products and services that a void barrier that have traditionally kept women from accessing loans or formal finance, such as collateral requirements, documentation requirements, cultural barriers and limited mobility. All the above-mentioned requirements affect women access to finance.

Studies and research done by many of the UN agencies such as World Bank, UNIFEM, indicating that gender inequalities in developing societies inhibit economic growth and development. A recent World Bank Report confirms that societies that discriminate on gender bases pay the cost of greater poverty, slower economic growth, weaker governance and a lower living standard of their people. The UNDP

found that there is strong relation between gender empowerment measure and gender related development indices and its human development index.

According to CIDA gender policy “Attention to gender equality is essential to sound development practice and at the heart of economic and social progress.

Facilitating access to financial recourses will not only enable poor women to earn higher income and have control over their resources but will also build their self-esteem and self-confidence. Empowering the poor in the first step in eradicating poverty and empowering women is a step towards the improvement of their socio-economic conditions of the family as such.

Section Three

2-3 Financial inclusion, Microfinance, as components of self-employment.: -

Financial inclusion is the availability and equality of opportunities to access financial services it refer to a process by which individuals and business can access appropriate, affordable, and timely financial products and services which include banking , loan ,equity, and insurance products it is a bath to enhance inclusiveness in economic growth by enabling the unbanked population to access the means for savings, investment, and insurance towards improving household income and reducing income in equality.

Financial inclusion efforts typically target those who are unbanked and underbanked and direct sustainable financial services to them.

Financial inclusion entails going beyond merely opening a bank account. Banked individuals can be excluded from financial services. Having more inclusive financial systems has been linked to stronger and more sustainable economic growth and development, thus achieving financial inclusion has become a priority for many countries across the globe.

In 2018, about 1.7 billion adults were estimated to lack a bank account. Among those who are unbanked a significant number are women and poor people in rural areas and often those who are excluded from financial institutions, face discrimination and belong to vulnerable or marginalized populations.

CHAPTER THREE

Poverty and Social Development In the Sudan

3.1. Introduction

Sudan is a country with a potential for growth despite all its diversities. It is envisaged that the burden of poverty unevenly distributed between the different regions of the country. This in its self-constitutes a real challenge to development at large. Sudan is rich in terms of its natural and human resources. Unfortunately, a high percentage of the population is under poverty lines. Poverty remains unacceptably high, the number of poor people remained roughly constant as the population increased, and the human development indicators remained low simultaneously. Problems of development since post-independence are characterized with: low productivity, high unemployment, high illiteracy rate, high inflation rate and consequently low living standard. The obstacles of economic growth and the absence of the basic social needs over the years have adversely affected development plans. The effects of civil war and tribal conflict in the southern and western parts of the country have severe setback on political stability and social integration.

3.2. The Structure of the Sudan's economy

Sudan's poverty challenge is characterized by the poor record of economic growth prior to 1990s, while the Sudanese economy was dominated by the services sector. High inequality in income and assets ownership, and inadequate access to basic social services, which result in low levels of human resources development and low agricultural productivity. Sudan is an agricultural country where the agricultural sector contributes 45% to the National Domestic Product (NDP), 54% employment, 85% of the export earning Least Developing Countries & Document of Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning (LDC & Document of MOFEP 2003). The industrial sector contributes 23% which increased due to oil production the services sector contributes 31% which has progressively decreased due to the policies that favour productive sector through provision of financing and reduction of Government spending and budgetary control (ibid).

3-4-Micro-finance Extension in the Sudanese Banks

The number of the commercial Sudanese banks working in micro-finance reached 20 banks. According to the financial polices of the central bank the 10% was allocated for micro credit as stated in the financial policy of 2005.

Despite differences in loans size between these banks, and the number of financed projects and the deficit rates, with the exception of the saving banks all these

banks are common on the weak rates of microfinance out of the grand total of its finance. The table below illustrate this in details:

Table (5.1) Illustrates the Distribution of Microfinance in Sudanese Banks

No	Bank name	Not project		Deficit rate		% of microfinance	
		2003	2004	2003	2004	2003	2004
1	Agricultural bank	653	864	29	15	0,82	1,14
2	Khartoum bank	15	5	0,03	-	0,02	0,00
3	Nileen bank	1,995	1,019	13	17	3,65	2,24
4	Saving bank	2,618	5,426	24	18	23,2	29,88
5	Cooperative development bank	32	51	-	0,05	0,09	0,13
6	Sudanese French bank	36	9	0,08	54	0,17	0,02
7	Central bank of Sudan	37	46	2	2	0,4	0,60
8	Islamic Tudamon bank	23	14	1	1	0,04	0,02
9	Islamic Sudanese bank	160	140	5	3	0,65	0,05
10	Elbaraka Islamic bank	55	60	-	-	0,08	0,05
11	Export development bank	150	125	5	14	5,36	3,64
12	Sudie Sudanese bank	-	-	-	-	0,01	0,00
13	National labor	55	33	3	0,35	0,61	0,19
14	Alshamal Islamic bank	56	99	-	6	047	0,63
15	Real Estate bank	-	1	-	-	0,00	0,01
16	Farmer commercial	1547	1,470	3	3	1,00	055
17	Animal Resources	54	24	9	16	0,09	0,05
18	Omdurman National	140	54	1	-	0,03	0,01
19	Ivori bank	-	4	-	-	0,00	0,12
20	Gadarif for investment	2	-	-	-	0,04	0,00

The central bank of Sudan statistics refers to the increasing in the total of micro-finance service in the Sudanese banks from 3 milliard in 2003 to more than 4 milliard in the year 2004. Despite this increase micro-finance percent still not more than 1% in most banks, with the exception of the Saving and Social Development bank, Export Development bank, Elnelleen and Sudanese Agriculture Bank. The number of the

financed projects increased by more than 7 thousand projects to 9 thousand projects for the same period. The 1990s witnessed the emergency of the micro-finance industry in most of the Sudanese commercial and specialized banks. It is worth mentioning that more than 75% of the finance these banks confined to the individual and group projects, where as 26% of them finance individual projects only despite the fact that group finance proved world wide to be more secure in repayment and in profit as it consider group collateral. According to the interview conducted for the purpose of this study the ceiling of finance for individuals found to be ranged between 500,000 dinars to more than 80% of the banks branches; in most of the Sudanese banks it is evident that there is no interest in saving neither from the banks nor from the side of the clients, although saving is consider the essence of micro-finance.

The majority of the banks managers who were interviewed the interview revealed that clients money is used as main source of lending this why they usually reluctant in financing the poor to avoid the risk of failure in repayment.

About 100% of the banks require check as a collateral or, house the thing which reflect the reasons of the lack of bank access for the poor. In addition, most of the commercial banks required a bank account, and visibility study plus guarantee, collateral for its financial lending, the things which is beyond the capability of the poor especially poor women.

Commercial banks concerned very much in the repayment of the capital. Banks did not concern with rescheduling. Once the clients fail to repay the loan, then they will send them to the court.

All the banks' managers interviewed with the exception of Elzahra and Elbraka bank, there is no specified target groups.

All banks studied charged high interest rate which we consider beyond the poor capabilities, this rate is high, although charging higher rates might have allowed them to increase their services and increase their revenues, banks managers generally fear the negative effects that could result from charging the most disadvantaged entrepreneurs.

As far as guarantees are concern all banks required a asset or cheque guarantee. No bank had flexible collateral.

In summary, the experience of banks in the Sudan in microfinance indicates that banks wishing to improve the poor people's access to their services but they are hindered by the central bank policies.

The opportunities for microfinance in the Sudan is very large due to the potential demand, in the country. The banks services covered only approximately 5% of the needs required.

CHAPTER Four

Summary, Results and Recommendations

6.1. Summary

More than one billion people in the world live on less than one dollar a day. In total, 2.7 billion struggle to survive on less than two dollars per day. Poverty in the developing world, however, goes far beyond income poverty. It means having to walk more than one mile everyday simply to collect water and firewood; it means suffering diseases that were eradicated from rich countries decades ago. Every year eleven million children die-most under the age of five and more than six million from completely preventable causes like malaria, diarrhea and pneumonia.

In some deeply impoverished nations less than half of the children are in primary school and under 20 percent go to secondary school. Around the world, a total of 114 million children do not get even a basic education and 584 million women are illiterate.

The Study pertained to the following conclusion as key socio-economic and forces that explain low income and high levels of poverty in the country:

- Level of development and essential features of the macro-economy.
- Educational attainment, Employment, unemployment, earning, international migration and poverty measures.
- Regional dimension of poverty.
- The gender dimension of poverty.
- The Burdens of man-made and natural disasters.

Against this background one could summarized the following findings as social dimensions in the area of poverty in the Sudan:

- a) High fertility levels with high dependency rate among poor families.
- b) Large size of the households and the level of poverty and impoverishment.

- c) The shrinking economic base in the rural sector encouraging rural to urban migration, leading to increasing pressures on urban centers, reflected in limited social services.
- d) Child labor as a particular manifestation of poverty.
- e) Some evidence of feminization of poverty, in terms of vulnerability of female headed households to poverty more likely than male headed household.
- f) The increasing unemployment rate among young graduates which threaten the social fabrics and its security.
- g) The impact of tribal conflict, civil wars, in terms of exacerbating existing poverty phenomenon.

6.2. Results

The study reveals the following results:

- (1) In the Sudan access to credit allows poor people to take the advantage of economic opportunities.
- (2) By reducing vulnerability and increasing earnings and savings, financial services allow poor households to make the transformation from "every-day survival" to "planning for the future."

6.3. Recommendations

Relying on the above the following recommendations could be suggested:

6.3.1. In the area of poverty reduction

- 11) An urgent need to conduct the poverty map for the Sudan.
- 12) Recognizing the importance of labor as an asset of the poor, a labor intensive development intervention should be adopted.
- 13) Promoting self-employment as a poverty alleviation intervention.
- 14) At the macro-level the identification of the socio-economic policies and pro-poor strategies is essential as an anti-poverty strategy. A national poverty alleviation strategy is a must.
- 15) At the micro-level a poverty alleviation plan of action is a must.
- 16) Drawing attention to the importance of education and equity of opportunities and choice.

- 17) Combating unemployment in its different types and among different segment in the society.
- 18) Identification of the term poverty there is no concrete definition of poverty in Sudan yet. The Ministry of Welfare adopted the definition of had alkifaya and had alkaf as the poverty definition.
- 19) The necessity of the identification of the poverty line in Sudan as the Academician adopted the global definition (less than one dollar a day) poverty line, so there is important need to define both poverty and those suffering from it.
- 20) Facilitating access to microfinance as a poverty alleviation intervention

6.3.2. Recommendations in The Area of Gender

The central recommendations in the area of gender are as follows:

- 10) Ensure women and men equal access to resources, education, labor, land, capital and technology.
- 11) Ensure women access to micro- finance, credit and enterprise development.
- 12) Avoiding the stereotypic views which perpetuating gender-based sectoral and occupational segregation.
- 13) Regulating women work in the informal sector where women represents the bulk of the disadvantaged labor force.
- 14) Promote women ability in decision making and their organization in women unions, and community based organizations.
- 15) Removing legislation barriers which perpetuate women subordination and gender gaps in income/capability poverty.
- 16) Enhancing gender capabilities literacy, formal education, market-relevant skill training particularly vocational training.
- 17) Advocating at the micro level for a conducive environment and to a better understanding of poverty gender specific aspects.

- 18) Advocating for the design of programs addressing socio-economic equity in the community, translated into development intervention at the community in a sustainable micro project.

6.3.3. Recommendations in the Area of Micro-finance& Financial Inclusion:

Against this background the following recommendations could be considered:

6. Make available effective access of the poor and make the financial system respond to the demand for microfinance.
7. At the micro level the development of an effective competent financial institutions is essential and strengthen financial infrastructure.
8. At the macro level the development of policies and creation of enabling environment that protects and supports the development of the financial sector for the poor are essential. Developing a national inclusion strategy is vital.
9. At the local level the development of the required institutional capacity building in terms of human capital and financial infrastructure.

According to my experience the microfinance industry in the Sudan lacks:

- a) Clear industry standards based on “best practices” of microfinance.
- b) Availability of data base and market information.
- c) Coordination among donors and government.
- d) An enabling environment and regulations.
- e) Strong intermediaries' institutions and support programs.

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